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Slightly Elevated Ammonia with Severe Neurological Findings in an Ornithine Transcarbamylase Deficiency Case

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ABSTRACT

Ornithine transcarbamylase deficiency (OTCD) is the most common subtype of urea cycle disorders with X-linked inheritance. Here, we present the clinical follow-up of a 9.5-year-old patient diagnosed with OTCD, who exhibited severe neurological symptoms despite a slightly elevated ammonia level. The patient had prior episodes of asymptomatic mild hyperammonemia (100-200 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) and severe hyperammonemia (645 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) with ataxia and drowsiness, successfully managed with ammonia scavenger treatments. The patient, who was followed up regularly and had good dietary compliance, was admitted to the emergency service due to agitated behavior, ataxia, and a tendency to sleep. The first ammonia level at admission was 127.7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Although additional oral doses of sodium benzoate, sodium phenylbutyrate, L-arginine, and carnitine were given, followed by intravenous sodium benzoate and sodium phenylacetate, no significant decrease in ammonia was achieved, and the neurological findings progressed. There was no other trauma, intoxication, meningitis, encephalitis, dietary disruption, or high protein intake that would explain the patient's comatose state. Brain MRI and fundus examination revealed no pathology. Despite ammonia levels ranging between 127.7 and 197.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, the decision for hemodialysis was made due to the progression of neurological findings and the comatose state. The pre-dialysis ammonia level increased to 905 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ during hemodialysis preparation. Serum amino acids measured before dialysis during the hyperammonemia attack were alanine: 554.27 (144-557), glutamine: 986.9 (333-809) mmol/L, and urine organic acid analysis resulted in orotic acid as 2.29 mmol/molcrea (0-11). In the second hour of hemodialysis, the patient's ammonia level decreased to 297 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and due to the development of hypotension, the procedure was terminated. She was intubated, and inotropic support was started. After hemodialysis was discontinued, the ammonia level decreased to 138.9 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and rebound hyperammonemia did not develop. However, the patient, whose Glasgow coma score dropped to 3, died at the 48th hour after dialysis due to cardiac arrest. While our patient previously had attacks with higher ammonia levels but milder neurological findings, in her last admission, she presented with a severe neurological clinic disproportionate to her ammonia level. Despite a decrease in ammonia levels post-dialysis, the patient's condition deteriorated rapidly, leading to cardiac arrest and death. This case underscores the challenge of managing severe neurological manifestations in OTCD, even with seemingly moderate ammonia levels, highlighting the potential need for early dialysis regardless of ammonia levels. This case contributes to the limited literature on this topic.

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Introduction

Ornithine transcarbamylase deficiency (OTCD) is an inherited metabolic disease within the subgroup of urea cycle disorders.¹ The disease is inherited in an X-linked manner, and clinical findings are observed in both males and females.¹ Here, the clinical course and management steps of a 9.5-year-old girl patient who presented to the emergency department with severe neurological symptoms despite mild hyperammonemia and severe changes in consciousness incompatible with hyperammonemia will be presented.

Case

A 9.5-year-old female patient was diagnosed with OTCD three years ago, based on both metabolic and genetic tests, due to a tendency to sleep and irritability attacks, and her ammonia level was successfully reduced with oral and IV ammonia scavenger treatments due to her past high-level hyperammonemia (645 $\mu\text{mol/l}$) attacks. The patient was able to perform daily activities and self-care without assistance. Body weight: 20 kg (<3p, -2.6 SDS), Height: 123 cm (<3p, -2.0 SDS). The same day, after weakness and restlessness that started at home in the morning, the patient was admitted to the emergency service in the afternoon with complaints of an ataxic gait, subsequent confusion, meaningless conversations, and a tendency to sleep. The patient, whose spontaneous eyes were open, her pupils were isochoric, and her direct and indirect light reflexes were positive, had a distracting response that could not be localized to painful stimuli and meaningless sounds. Glasgow's coma score was 10 points. There was no suspicion of intoxication, dietary incompatibility, high protein intake, fever, vomiting, or seizure in her history. She was using sodium benzoate (300mg/kg/day), sodium phenylbutyrate (420 mg/kg/day), and L-arginine (225 mg/kg/day) medications regularly. There were no signs of meningeal irritation during the physical examination. The patient's complete blood count, biochemistry (AST: 22 u/L ALT: 14 u/L), CRP, procalcitonin, and carboxyhemoglobin levels were within normal limits. In the blood gas, there was respiratory alkalosis (pH: 7.45, PCO₂: 28, HCO₃: 21.8), which is expected in hyperammonemia. Her ammonia level was 127.7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ upon admission, and she showed signs of severe inappropriate changes in consciousness, although mild hyperammonemia. A brain MRI was performed on the patient, and no pathological findings suggestive of diffusion restriction, brain edema, or pseudostroke were detected. No papilledema was detected in the fundus examination. The patient's L-arginine, sodium benzoate, and sodium phenylbutyrate treatments were continued enterally by inserting a nasogastric tube. An additional dose of 250 mg/kg of sodium benzoate and sodium phenylbutyrate was given enterally in addition to the maintenance doses. Protein intake was stopped, and the fluid was adjusted to a high glucose infusion rate of 6 mg/kg/min. After 4 hours, the control ammonia level resulted in 135.1 $\mu\text{mol/l}$. There was no change in the clinical findings. The patient was started on crystallized insulin infusion for anabolic effect and lipid infusion for calorie support. A central catheter was inserted into the patient, whose control ammonia level was 197.5 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, and iv sodium benzoate and iv na phenylacetate 250 mg/kg loading was started. A maintenance dose was applied with the same dosage. N-carbamylglutamate was given enterally at 100 mg/kg. However, the patient's Glasgow coma score decreased to 8 (she was opening his eyes with painful stimuli, making meaningless sounds, and moving aimlessly to painful stimuli), her pupils became isochoric mid-dilated, and the light reflex response decreased. No papilledema was detected in the control fundus examination. No pathological findings were detected in the follow-up brain MRI. Since the patient's control ammonia level decreased to 157.4 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, clinical follow-up continued, but hemodialysis preparations were started.

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In the follow-up, the control ammonia level was 642.6 $\mu\text{mol/L}$; catheter revision was performed due to insufficient catheter diameter for hemodialysis, and she was taken to hemodialysis with 905.0 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. During hemodialysis, the ammonia level decreased to 297.0 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in the 2nd hour. Hemodialysis was terminated at the 2nd hour due to the development of hypotension. After dialysis, the decrease in ammonia continued up to 138.9 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Rebound hyperammonemia, which can be seen after dialysis, was not observed. However, due to hypotension developed during dialysis, she was intubated and received noradrenaline and adrenaline infusion from that moment on. The patient had no response to painful stimuli, pupils were fixed and dilated, and there was no light reflex response. The patient's resistant hypotension continued, her Glasgow coma score dropped to 3, cardiac arrest developed, and she became exitus in the 48th hour after hemodialysis.

There was no positive result in the patient's blood and urine cultures. Acute phase reactants did not increase during follow-up. No other cause was detected other than hyperammonemia that could explain the change in consciousness and comatose state. When the patient's ammonia level was 642.6 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, the serum amino acids ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) were Alanine: 554.27 (144-557), Glutamine: 986.9 (333-809), Citrulline: 3.79 (6-49), Arginine: 37.64 (45-125), and urine organic acid analysis resulted in orotic acid: 2.29 mmol/mol creat (0-11). At the patient's routine check-up one month before the attack, in the asymptomatic period, serum amino acids ($\mu\text{mol/L}$) were Alanine: 415.82 (144-557), Glutamine: 612.19 (333-809), Citrulline: 8.79 (6-49), Arginine: 130.46 (45-125) and urine organic acid analysis resulted in orotic acid: 0 mmol/mol creat (0-11).

Discussion

Despite the patient's stupor at first admission, her ammonia level was 127.7, and she had only slightly high hyperammonemia. The patient, who is under regular follow-up, had previous asymptomatic outpatient follow-ups with similar ammonia levels. Once, she applied to the outpatient clinic with complaints of only mild ataxia and mild drowsiness, with an ammonia level of 645 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. She was admitted to the intensive care unit. Her ammonia level was lowered in 4 hours with iv benzoate and iv phenylacetate infusion. There was no need for dialysis, and her mild clinical findings improved within hours. In her last episode, it was very difficult to interpret and manage such mild but resistant hyperammonemia and such severe clinical findings. In hyperammonemia treatment guidelines, hemodialysis preparation is recommended when the ammonia level is between 250 -500 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.² Additionally, the hemodialysis process has its own complications.³ Literature shows that continuous venovenous hemodiafiltration is more successful in this group of patients.³ However, only the hemodialysis method could be applied to our patient because this was the fastest treatment that could be used in our intensive care unit. Hypotension that developed during the procedure could not be treated despite termination of the procedure and inotropic support. Although the patient's ammonia level was not within the dialysis limit in the guideline when she first arrived, hemodialysis could have been performed earlier (between ammonia levels 197.5 and 157.4 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) due to the severe change in consciousness and neurological findings.

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Similarly, there is another case of OTC deficiency described in the literature with severe neurological findings in mild hyperammonemia.⁴ This patient was admitted to the emergency department in a lethargic state when the ammonia level was 191.4 $\mu\text{mol/L}$.⁴ Although the ammonia level decreased after ammonia-lowering treatments, she was first taken to hemodialysis due to the development of class 2-3 coma symptoms.⁴ She could not tolerate this in the 3rd hour of dialysis, and the clinical condition worsened and then was applied continuous venovenous hemodiafiltration for 16 hours.⁴ During the follow-up of this patient, her neurological findings improved after dialysis, and she continued to follow up without any sequelae.⁴ Some authors suggest that hemodialysis can be performed in cases where the ammonia level is lower than that of the classical approach guidelines, $>180 \mu\text{mol/L}$.^{5,6} In the metabolic examinations taken when the ammonia level of our patient increased to 642 $\mu\text{mol/L}$, despite severe hyperammonemia, there were not significantly high serum glutamine and alanine levels in serum analysis. It was also interesting that there was no increased urinary orotic acid level. Since our patient was a patient with a known diagnosis, metabolic tests were not taken when she presented with her first attack, which prevented us from understanding whether this was treatment-related or not. However, in another case in the literature, it was stated that plasma glutamine and urinary orotic acid levels were normal at admission.⁴ This situation also brings to mind whether another accumulated substance, which we have not yet defined and can be cleared by dialysis, may be causing the neurological findings. With the development of omic technologies, it may be worth investigating the serum samples of patients with OTC deficiency during the attack in terms of an accumulated substance we have not yet identified.⁷ Pseudostroke-like brain MRI can also be seen in OTC deficiency patients. There was no involvement in the brain MRIs taken upon our patient's arrival and 24 hours later. There were no physical examination findings such as hemiparesis or facial asymmetry. This reduces the possibility of a stroke-like attack triggering a comatose state, which can be seen in OTC deficiency.^{8,9}

Conclusion

OTC deficiency is the most common type of urea cycle disorder. It is a disease that can develop hyperammonemia with a wide variety of triggering factors, causing clinical findings ranging from headache to coma and severe morbidity and mortality. Although it is stated that high ammonia levels are correlated with clinical findings and the risk of sequelae, in a small number of cases like ours, there may be severe neurological findings disproportionate to high ammonia levels. There is still insufficient data in the literature about managing such patients or whether there is a possible different metabolite that accumulates other than ammonia, causing severe neurological findings.

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